

Epistemic (In)Justice

That which has a name comes to exist: sexual harassment

There is an old Basque proverb that says *izena duenak izana du* – “that which has a name comes to exist.” It captures the heart of epistemic injustice, and it also frames the story behind the phrase sexual harassment. In 1975, Carmita Wood quit her job at Cornell University. She had worked there for eight years, supporting four children, but her supervisor, physicist Boyce McDaniel, who had participated in the Manhattan Project, made her daily life unbearable. He bombarded her with sexual comments, found excuses to brush against her, and at the office Christmas party cornered her in the lift and kissed her on the mouth.

When she applied for unemployment benefits, she could not bring herself to explain why she had left, and in the form she simply wrote “personal reasons.” The request was denied. Even when she tried to tell her story, she had no recognised language to describe it. The absence of a name made the harm invisible.

She told her story to Lin Farley, co-founder of *Working Women United*. Farley not only provided legal help but also organised a Speak Out. Preparing posters, they realised no clear phrase existed for what they wanted to denounce. Out of that brainstorming session came a new expression: sexual harassment.

What is epistemic injustice?

Carmita’s experience shows what philosophers call epistemic injustice: it arises either when prejudice leads people to dismiss someone’s word, or when society has no shared concepts to interpret and express what that person is going through.

Miranda Fricker, who developed the concept, distinguishes two main forms (Fricker, 2007):

- **Testimonial injustice:** This happens when a speaker is trusted less because of bias about their identity – gender, race, class. Think of the countless women who, for years, reported severe menstrual pain. Doctors often dismissed them as stressed or overly sensitive. Many of these women had endometriosis, but the diagnosis was delayed by seven or eight years because gender prejudice made their suffering less believable.
- **Hermeneutical injustice:** It occurs when there are no words or frameworks to interpret an experience. Obstetric violence is one example: until recently, women had no term to describe the humiliating practices some endured during childbirth. Without a name, such practices appeared “normal.”

Why this matters to me

The idea of epistemic injustice is especially powerful in the digital age. Social media platforms rely on moderation and ranking systems powered by artificial intelligence. These systems automate old biases and scale them up.

Consider this: activists from Black Lives Matter and Palestinian creators have repeatedly complained that their posts about protests or human rights violations lose visibility on Instagram and X (formerly Twitter). Algorithms designed to hide “sensitive” content end up silencing testimonies, subtly stripping their words of credibility. That is testimonial injustice at work.

A second case: in 2020, Facebook was heavily criticised for failing to treat Holocaust denial as hate speech. Its systems lacked the interpretative framework to see that denying a documented genocide is itself a form of violence against Jewish communities. Only after campaigns such as #StopHateForProfit did Facebook change its policy. This was a clear instance of hermeneutical injustice.

By naming these dynamics, Fricker helped repair an injustice of her own time: she gathered scattered and unnamed experiences into a single concept, making them visible and, in doing so, embedding the idea in our moral vocabulary. Since then, thinkers such as Kristie Dotson, José Medina and myself, have expanded the field, showing that epistemic injustice is not a static idea but an evolving critical lens.

References

Fricker, Miranda (2007). *Epistemic Injustice: Power and the Ethics of Knowing*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780198237907.001.0001>

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